

Analyzing the Popularity of a Music Genre Among Students in a Suburban North Carolina School through Statistical Methods.

Abstract:

This study aimed to determine the proportion of students in a suburban high school in North Carolina who prefer rap/hip hop music. A random sample of 214 students from a population of 2200 was surveyed using a Google Form. The results revealed that 39.8% of the sample reported rap/hip hop as their favorite genre. A 99% confidence interval for the proportion of all students in the school who like rap music was calculated, ranging from 31.16% to 48.44%. The findings suggest that rap music is a popular genre, with an estimated 685 to 1065 students in the school likely favoring rap/hip hop. This study highlights the potential cultural significance of rap and hip hop music among teenagers, shedding light on adolescent music preferences in suburban schools. These insights can inform further research and cater to the needs of educators, researchers, and marketers targeting this demographic.

Keywords: Music preferences, student surveys, confidence interval, statistical analysis, population proportion, music genres, cultural influence, adolescent behavior, statistical inference, AP Statistics, North Carolina, suburban school, sample proportion, music trends.

Introduction:

The role of music, particularly through devices like AirPods, is a common occurrence in high school. Observing high school students listening to music throughout the school day sparked a growing curiosity about the genres they preferred listening to. With an abundance of music styles available, it became increasingly intriguing to explore which genres dominated students' preferences. This led to a specific interest in identifying the most popular music genres among students. In a world where digital music consumption is almost everywhere in the world, understanding the preferred music genres among adolescents can provide valuable insights into their cultural and social behaviors.

This study specifically investigates the popularity of rap/hip hop music in a suburban North Carolina school, where diverse cultural influences may shape musical preferences. This research contributes to the growing body of knowledge on adolescent music preferences, particularly in suburban settings. By understanding these preferences, educators, researchers, and marketers can better cater to this demographic, whether through educational tools, events, or products. The primary objective of this study is to estimate the proportion of students in a suburban high school who prefer rap music. Specifically, the goal is to calculate a 99% confidence interval for this proportion. The study focuses on students from a single suburban school in North Carolina. While the sample size was relatively large (214 students), the results

may not be entirely generalizable to other regions or schools with different cultural dynamics.

This study is grounded in statistical analysis using inferential methods, specifically focusing on proportion estimation and confidence intervals. A random sample of 214 students was surveyed about their favorite music genres. Data was analyzed using basic statistical tools to estimate the population proportion of students who prefer rap music, with a 99% confidence interval calculated. Given the importance of understanding youth culture, the study specifically investigates the popularity of rap/hip hop music in a suburban North Carolina school. This research contributes to a growing body of knowledge on adolescent music preferences in suburban settings. Aiming to accurately estimate the proportion of students who prefer rap music, the study uses a 99% confidence interval to ensure a high level of certainty in the population's preferences.

Methods:

Research Design: This is an observational, cross-sectional study, as data were collected at one point in time from a random sample of students.

Participants or Sample: The sample consisted of 214 students selected randomly from a school of 2200 students. Participants were asked to indicate their favorite music genre from a list of common options, including rap/hip hop.

- Rock
- Pop
- Rap/ hip-pop
- Classical music
- Country
- Jazz
- Folk music
- R&B
- Heavy metal
- Other: _____

Figure 1 - Music Genre Options in the Google Form

Data Collection: Data was collected via a Google Form survey distributed in person to students in the school. No personal information was collected to maintain anonymity.

Variables and Measurements: The main variable is the proportion of students who like rap music, measured as the percentage of survey respondents who selected rap/hip hop.

Procedure: Participants were randomly approached in common areas (e.g., lunch line, hallway) and asked to fill out the survey. After data cleaning to remove invalid responses, the final analysis was conducted.

Data Analysis: The proportion of students who prefer rap music was calculated. A 99% confidence interval was then computed for the population proportion, using standard inferential statistics.

Ethical Considerations: Ethical approval was not required for this study, as no personal information was collected, and participation was voluntary. Informed consent was obtained by informing participants about the nature of the survey.

The study found that 39.8% of the 214 students in the sample prefer rap music. A 99% confidence interval for the proportion of all students in the school who prefer rap music was calculated using statistical analysis.

Figure 2 - pie chart distribution of the Google Form Responses

Statistical Analysis:

To estimate the proportion of students at the school who prefer rap music, a 99% confidence interval for the population proportion was calculated based on the data collected from a random sample of 214 students. The following steps outline the mathematical procedures used:

1. **Sample Proportion (p):** The proportion of students in the sample who prefer rap music was calculated as:
 $p = 39.8/100 = 0.398$
2. **Standard Error (SE):** The standard error for a proportion is calculated using the formula:

$$SE = \sqrt{\frac{p(1-p)}{n}}$$

where:

- p is the sample proportion,
- n is the sample size.

Figure 3 - standard error formula

Using the above equation, the standard error is equal to 0.03346.

3. **Critical Value (z):** For a 99% confidence level, the critical z-value is 2.576 (based on the standard normal distribution).

4. **Margin of Error (ME):** The margin of error is calculated using the formula:

$$ME = z \times SE$$

Figure 4 - margin of error formula

Using the above equation, the Margin Of Error is equal to 0.08619

5. **Confidence Interval:** The 99% confidence interval for the population proportion of students who prefer rap music is given by:

$$p \pm ME$$

Figure 5 - confidence interval formula

Substituting the values in the above equation,

$$0.398 \pm 0.08619$$

6. Population Estimate: To estimate the number of students at the school who prefer rap music, the confidence interval is multiplied by the total population of students (2200):

- Lower bound: 0.48419
- Upper bound: 0.31181

By multiplying the lower and upper bounds of the confidence interval (0.31181 and 0.48419) by the total school population (2200 students), the estimated number of students who prefer rap music ranges between 685 and 1065 students. This population estimate is grounded in the calculated confidence interval and reflects the expected proportion of rap music listeners in the entire school.

Results:

The 99% confidence interval suggests that, with 99% certainty, between 31.18% and 48.41% of all students in the school prefer rap music. This means that the true proportion of students who like rap music is very likely to fall within this range, offering valuable insights into the music preferences of the school population.

Discussion:

Restatement of Key Findings: This study found that rap music is a favorite among a significant proportion of students in a suburban school in North Carolina. The 99% confidence interval suggests that a substantial number of students across the school likely prefer this genre.

Implications and Significance: The results provide insights into music preferences among adolescents, suggesting that rap music holds a prominent place in their cultural and social lives. This information could be useful for school event planning, as well as for music industry professionals targeting this demographic.

Connection to Objectives: The research objectives were met by successfully estimating the proportion of students who prefer rap music and calculating a reliable confidence interval.

Recommendations: Further studies could explore the reasons behind the popularity of rap music in different age groups or school environments, potentially comparing suburban and urban schools.

Limitations: While the study was conducted using a random sample of 214 students, it is important to note that the results may not be fully generalizable to other schools, especially those with different cultural dynamics or regions. The study is also limited by the fact that the survey only addressed students' music preferences without investigating deeper motivations for these preferences.

Closing Thought: Understanding the music preferences of teenagers not only reflects cultural trends but also offers valuable insights into their social behaviors and values, suggesting areas for future research in cultural and behavioral studies.

References :

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